

PVsyst - Simulation report

Standalone system

Project: ITS Surabaya

Variant: New simulation variant

Standalone system with batteries

System power: 39.2 kWp

ITS Surabaya_Majdi - Indonesia

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Variant: New simulation variant

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Project summary

Geographical Site ITS Surabaya_Majdi Indonesia	Situation Latitude -7.28 °S Longitude 112.80 °E Altitude 6 m Time zone UTC+7	Project settings Albedo 0.20
Weather data ITS Surabaya_Majdi ITS - Synthetic		

System summary

Standalone system	Standalone system with batteries		
PV Field Orientation Fixed plane Tilt/Azimuth 10 / 0 °	User's needs Daily household consumers Constant over the year Average 210 kWh/Day		
System information		Battery pack	
PV Array Nb. of modules 56 units Pnom total 39.2 kWp		Technology Lithium-ion, NCA Nb. of units 8 units Voltage 101 V Capacity 1072 Ah	

Results summary

Useful energy from solar 61662 kWh/year	Specific production 1573 kWh/kWp/year	Perf. Ratio PR 79.44 %
Missing Energy 14942 kWh/year	Available solar energy 63520 kWh/year	Solar Fraction SF 80.48 %
Excess (unused) 193 kWh/year		

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General parameters

Standalone system		Standalone system with batteries	
PV Field Orientation		Sheds configuration	
Orientation		No 3D scene defined	
Fixed plane			
Tilt/Azimuth	10 / 0 °		
User's needs		Models used	
Daily household consumers		Transposition	Perez
Constant over the year		Diffuse	Perez, Meteonorm
Average		Circumsolar	separate
Average		210 kWh/Day	

PV Array Characteristics

PV module		Battery	
Manufacturer	Generic	Manufacturer	Tesla
Model	Mono 700 Wp Twin half-cells bifacial (Original PVsyst database)	Model	Powerwall2
Unit Nom. Power	700 Wp	Technology	Lithium-ion, NCA
Number of PV modules	56 units	Nb. of units	4 in parallel x 2 in series
Nominal (STC)	39.2 kWp	Discharging min. SOC	10.0 %
Modules	7 string x 8 In series	Stored energy	98.1 kWh
At operating cond. (50°C)		Battery Pack Characteristics	
Pmpp	36.0 kWp	Voltage	101 V
U mpp	309 V	Nominal Capacity	1072 Ah (C10)
I mpp	116 A	Temperature	Fixed 30 °C
Controller		Battery Management control	
Universal controller		Threshold commands as	SOC calculation
Technology	MPPT converter	Charging	SOC = 0.96 / 0.80
Temp coeff.	-5.0 mV/°C/Elem.	Discharging	SOC = 0.10 / 0.35
Converter			
Maxi and EURO efficiencies	97.0 / 95.0 %		
Total PV power			
Nominal (STC)	39 kWp		
Total	56 modules		
Module area	174 m²		
Cell area	163 m²		

Array losses

Thermal Loss factor		DC wiring losses		Serie Diode Loss				
Module temperature according to irradiance		Global array res.	44 mΩ	Voltage drop	0.7 V			
Uc (const)	20.0 W/m²K	Loss Fraction	1.5 % at STC	Loss Fraction	0.2 % at STC			
Uv (wind)	0.0 W/m²K/m/s							
Module Quality Loss		Module mismatch losses		Strings Mismatch loss				
Loss Fraction	-0.4 %	Loss Fraction	2.0 % at MPP	Loss Fraction	0.1 %			
IAM loss factor								
Incidence effect (IAM): Fresnel, AR coating, n(glass)=1.526, n(AR)=1.290								
0°	30°	50°	60°	70°	75°	80°	85°	90°
1.000	0.999	0.987	0.962	0.892	0.816	0.681	0.440	0.000

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Detailed User's needs

Daily household consumers, Constant over the year, average = 210 kWh/day

Annual values

	Nb.	Power	Use	Energy
		W	Hour/day	Wh/day
Lights for rooms and corridors	120	20/lamp	9.0	21600
AC_7000 unit	12	600/app	7.0	50400
AC_12000 unit	4	1200/app	8.0	38400
ECG machines centrifuges	50		3	2250
X-Ray machines	1		1	30000
Entilators, madical refrigrators	5	560 tot	24.0	67200
Stand-by consumers			24.0	24
Total daily energy				209874

Hourly distribution

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Main results

System Production

Useful energy from solar 61662 kWh/year
Available solar energy 63520 kWh/year
Excess (unused) 193 kWh/year

Perf. Ratio PR 79.44 %
Solar Fraction SF 80.48 %

Loss of Load

Time Fraction 0.6 %
Missing Energy 14942 kWh/year

Battery aging (State of Wear)

Cycles SOW 77.2 %
Static SOW 85.9 %

Normalized productions (per installed kWp)

Performance Ratio PR

Balances and main results

	GlobHor kWh/m ²	GlobEff kWh/m ²	E_Avail kWh	EUnused kWh	E_Miss kWh	E_User kWh	E_Load kWh	SolFrac ratio
January	155.0	143.2	4748	0.2	1842	4664	6506	0.716
February	123.2	117.1	3909	0.0	2112	3765	5876	0.641
March	155.0	152.5	5053	1.3	1595	4911	6506	0.755
April	144.0	146.9	4859	0.0	1609	4687	6296	0.744
May	158.1	166.5	5494	13.8	1186	5320	6506	0.818
June	150.0	161.6	5358	0.0	1060	5236	6296	0.832
July	145.7	155.3	5144	0.2	1492	5014	6506	0.771
August	179.8	187.6	6128	0.0	506	6001	6506	0.923
September	195.0	195.5	6292	158.2	335	5961	6296	0.947
October	207.7	200.2	6404	18.8	225	6281	6506	0.966
November	168.0	156.3	5083	0.0	1366	4930	6296	0.783
December	167.4	153.2	5046	0.2	1615	4891	6506	0.751
Year	1948.9	1936.0	63520	192.8	14942	61662	76604	0.805

Legends

GlobHor Global horizontal irradiation
 GlobEff Effective Global, corr. for IAM and shadings
 E_Avail Available Solar Energy
 EUnused Unused energy (battery full)
 E_Miss Missing energy
 E_User Energy supplied to the user
 E_Load Energy need of the user (Load)
 SolFrac Solar fraction (EUsed / ELoad)

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Loss diagram

- Global horizontal irradiation
- Global incident in coll. plane
- IAM factor on global
- Effective irradiation on collectors
- PV conversion
- Array nominal energy (at STC effic.)
- PV loss due to irradiance level
- PV loss due to temperature
- Module quality loss
- Mismatch loss, modules and strings
- Ohmic wiring loss
- Unused energy (battery full)
- Effective energy at the output of the array
- Converter Loss during operation (efficiency)
- Converter Loss due to power threshold
- Converter Loss over nominal conv. voltage
- Converter Loss due to voltage threshold
- Converter losses (effic, overload)
- Battery Storage
- Battery Stored Energy balance
- Battery efficiency loss
- Charge/Disch. Current Efficiency Loss
- Battery Self-discharge Current
- Energy from the sun
- Energy supplied to the user
- Energy need of the user (Load)

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Predef. graphs

Reference Incident Energy in Collector Plane

Normalized Production and Loss Factors

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Predef. graphs

Incident Irradiation Distribution

Incident Irradiation cumulative distribution

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Predef. graphs

Array Temperature vs. Effective Irradiance

Daily Input/Output diagram

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Predef. graphs

Daily Array Output Energy

Array Power Distribution

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Predef. graphs

State of charge daily distribution

